

Assessment of Oxidative Status in Fresh Edible Oils by Colorimetric Ferric Thiocyanate Method

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ABSTRACT

A rapid method for the quantitative determination of peroxide value (PV) of fresh edible oils by colorimetry is described. The determination of the peroxide value is the traditional and most used parameter for measuring the primary products of oxidative degradation. In addition, the analysis of the peroxide content of oil samples is a very analytical task because high peroxide levels in oils have been a threat to human health. The peroxide value is a suitable parameter for measuring the deterioration of quality of edible oils over prolonged heating. In the present study, a series of edible oils were taken and analyzed for PV, based on the co-oxidation of Fe(II) to Fe(III) by hydroperoxides from sample (fat) and the formation of the reddish Fe(III)-Thiocyanate complex which is read at 510 nm on a colorimeter.

Keywords: Peroxide value, Thiocyanate complex, edible oils, colorimetry

1. INTRODUCTION

A free radical reaction involving oxygen that leads to deterioration of oils which form off- flavours is an auto oxidation reaction[1]. Peroxide value of oils indicates concentration of peroxides in an oil or fat. It is useful for assessing the extent to which deterioration has advanced. Peroxide value can be used to identify oxidative rancidity in oils. Auto oxidation in oils leads to formation of toxic compounds which are injurious to health , unsaturated oils such as free fatty acids, triglycerides ,phospholipids undergo spontaneous oxidation reaction .They are chain reactions which form lipid hydro peroxides as a primary product .Peroxide value determines primary lipid hydro peroxide .It is usually expressed in mill equivalents (meq). Acceptable limit of PV is ,it should not be above 10–20 meq/kg fat to avoid rancidity flavor [2].Antioxidants in oils minimize auto oxidation reactions[3].Some of the official methods by which PV in oils can be analyzed are AOAC method ,American Oil Chemists Society Method ,Iodometric titrations, Spectrophotometric determination of ferric ions formed by oxidation of ferrous ions by peroxides in presence of xylenol orange also known as ferrous oxidation xylenol orange (FOX) method, International dairy federation method (IDF), number of techniques based on chromatography NMR spectroscopy also have been developed for determination of lipid peroxides.The present study is based on IDF method .This method is similar to MFOX method. IDF method uses simple, easily available chemicals, the method was found to be reliable and rapid.IDF method is sensitive requires less sample. It can be used as spot test for peroxide value in oils.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 MATERIALS AND METHODS

Groundnut oil, sesame oil , castor oil , olive oil , sunflower oil , rice bran oil, cow ghee, buffalo ghee , vanaspathi and coconut oil were purchased from local grocery. All the oils were stored at room temperature (25°C) under light and atmospheric conditions. All the chemicals and reagents (analytical grade) used were from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany), or SigmaAldrich Chemical Co. (St. Louis, MO), unless stated otherwise.

2.2 DETERMINATION OF PEROXIDE VALUE

IDF modified method for determination of PV. The proposed method was developed as a modification of the IDF standard method that is based on the co-oxidation of Fe(II) to Fe(III) by hydro peroxides and the formation of the reddish Fe(III)-Thiocyanate complex for colorimetric determination of PV.

To quantify the PV, the sample (200mg) was placed in a boiling tube and dissolved in 1 mL of chloroform/acetic acid (3:7), added 50µL Fe(II)solution and added 50µL of saturated ammonium thiocyanate solution to the sample. After 3 min, absorbance at 510nm was measured against a chloroform and aceticacid mixture as blank.

A reaction blank containing all the reagents, except the sample, was also performed, and the resulting absorbance value was subtracted from that of the sample.

Fe(II) stock solution was prepared by gently mixing a solution of 0.4 g of BaCl₂.2H₂O in 50 mL deionized water with a solution of 0.5 g of FeSO₄.7H₂O in 50 mL deionized water. Concentrated hydrochloric acid (2 mL) was added to the resulting solution, which was filtered and stored under cover. It is strongly recommended to prepare this solution as fresh as possible and check its stage before use by addition of a few drops of thiocyanate solution. Solution should be discarded if a pale pink color appears.

2.3 Fe(III) CALIBRATION

A working solution of Fe(III) 25 µg/mL was prepared from a standard stock solution [20mg Fe(III)/mL with 10N HCl by dilution with chloroform/acetic acid (3:7). For calibration, a set of solutions of increasing Fe(III) concentration in the range (1-25) µg/mL with 50 µL of saturated ammonium thiocyanate was prepared by successive dilutions of the working solution. The calibration curve was obtained by plotting absorbance (Abs in nm) vs. Fe(III) concentration. Peroxide value was calculated by using the following equation:

$$PV(\text{meq/kg}) = \left\{ \frac{(A_s - A_b) \times m}{55.84 \times m_o \times 2} \right\} \times 0.5$$

Where A_s is Absorbance of the sample

A_b is Absorbance of the blank

m is the slope, obtained from calibration curve

m_o is the mass in grams of the sample

55.84 is atomic weight of Iron

0.5 is the correction factor

The denominator gives the concentration of Fe²⁺ oxidised to Fe³⁺ in micrograms. The division by factor 2 is necessary to express the peroxide value as milliequivalents of oxygen, as mentioned in the IDF method [4].

3. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

In the present study, colorimetric technique has been used for the qualitative and quantitative evaluations of peroxide values of various edible oils. IDF method is used for Peroxide value evaluation. This method is based on the oxidation of Fe²⁺ ions in the presence of Ammonium thiocyanate. R-O-O-R of peroxide oxidize Fe²⁺ ions to Fe³⁺ ions. The Fe³⁺ ions resulting from oxidation are grouped and form a red complex. Its colorimetric intensity is measured at 510 nm, is directly proportional to the concentration of peroxide value in the sample. The amount of peroxide value of fats indicates the degree of primary oxidation and therefore its likeliness of becoming rancid. A lower number of peroxide value indicates a good quality of oil and a good preservation status [5].

A calibration curve (Figure 1) for 2-25 µg/ml Fe³⁺ were prepared by using 50 µl ammonium thiocyanate as indicated in the method and curve was linear.

The amount of peroxide was established in different oils, and ranged from 0.0069 mEq/kg (coconut oil) to 0.0325 mEq/kg (Vanaspathi) were listed in Table I. It can be observed that highest and lowest peroxide values were measured with vanaspathi and coconut oil respectively.

It can be observed that peroxide value is lowest in coconut oil when compared to other oils.

Table.1. Peroxide values of fresh edible oils

S.No	Name of oil sample	Peroxide value of fresh oil (Meq/Kg)
1	Ground nut oil	8.7×10^{-3}
2	Sunflower oil	4.18×10^{-3}
3	Coconut oil	0.689×10^{-3}
4	Sesameoil	2.916×10^{-3}
5	Rice bran oil	2.903×10^{-3}
6	Castor Oil	4.28×10^{-3}
7	Olive Oil	1.49×10^{-2}

8	Vanaspathi/ Hydrogenated vegetable Oil	3.25×10^{-2}
9	Buffallo Ghee	1.055×10^{-2}
10	Cow Ghee	3.14×10^{-3}

Calibration curve(Figure 1) Standard Fe⁺³ curve for determination of peroxide values by IDF method

CONCLUSION

Oxidation of oils is an important indicator for performance and shelf life of oils [6]. It is complex and depends on the light intensity and temperature. Initially oxidation in oils involves formation of hydro peroxides, peroxides, and then polymers of peroxides [7]. The PV is applicable for monitoring the formation of peroxides in the early stages of oxidation. Peroxide values of fresh edible oils are in the order coconut oil < rice bran oil < sesame oil < cow ghee < sunflower oil < castor oil < groundnut oil < buffalo ghee < olive oil < vanaspathi. This order indicates rancidity or deterioration in oils. Oils containing monounsaturated fats minimize artery blockage, supports the health of brain, heart and other organs and minimizes risk of diet-related ailments. Coconut oils are rich in monounsaturated fat [8] which helps to reduce cholesterol and triglyceride levels. The “Ceylon Medical Journal” notes that coconut fats do not contain artery-clogging trans fats, making coconut oil a healthy choice for those with heart problems

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